

Abundance And Species Composition of Common Mosquito Species in Makurdi Metropolis, Benue State Nigeria

*¹Alom, U.A., ²Manyi, M.M. and ²Azua, E.T.

Environmental Science Unit, Department of Botany, Joseph Sarwuan Tarka University, Makurdi, Nigeria
Department of Zoology, Joseph Sarwuan Tarka University, Makurdi, Nigeria

*Corresponding author: Alom Angus (angus.talom@gmail.com)

ABSTRACT

The aim of this study was to determine the abundance and species composition of common mosquito species in Makurdi metropolis. Larval sampling was carried out for one year (April 2021 – March 2022) from six locations using pole-mounted larval dipper with handle and clutches (WHO, 2005). The specimens were identified morphologically using standard descriptor guide aided by the use of taxonomic keys/aids, light microscope and mosquito experts. Data analysis was done using the Chi square and analysis of variance tools of the SPSS 20.0 version. Decision was taken at 95% confidence limit ($P \leq 0.05$ level of significance). From the study, *Culex quinquefasciatus* recorded the highest abundance of 2418 (56.0%) among all the species found out of a total number of 4,320 samples collected within 12 months. Abundance of *Anopheles* mosquito was the same in all location since Chi-square analysis did not show significant association ($\chi^2 = 5.00$, $P = 0.416$ ($P > 0.05$)). However, Gboko road had the highest number of *Anopheles* mosquito samples of 397 (20.9%) dominated by *A. funestus* (21.8%) and *A. gambiae* (21.3%) while Kanshio location recorded the lowest with a total of 186 mosquitoes (9.8%). *Anopheles* mosquito was dominated by *A. gambiae* with a total number of 1,040 samples collected with prevalence of 24.1%. While *A. gambiae* was highest at High Level location (23.2%) *A. funestus* was mostly found at Wurukum location (22.2%). The population of *Anopheles* species was more predominant in the wet seasons (April- September, 2011) than during the dry season (October, 2011- March, 2022). *Culex quinquefasciatus* had its peaks of abundance in April, 2021 [265 (52.7%)] and March, 2022 [302 (58.9%)]. This information may be useful in the control of mosquito and malaria infection in Makurdi, Benue State.

Key words: Morphology, Abundance, *Anopheles*, *Culex*, Malaria control

INTRODUCTON

Malaria is a life-threatening disease caused and spread by Plasmodium parasite and female mosquito vectors, respectively (WHO, 2018). It is the world's most important parasitic disease of public health interest (Aribodor *et al.*, 2016). According to the latest world malaria report, African region continues to have an alarmingly high incidence rate of malaria – 92% of malaria cases and 93% of malaria deaths (WHO, 2018). Nigeria accounts for 25% of the cases in Africa (WHO, 2019). In Northwest Nigeria, a prevalence range of 60% to 65% has been reported in different studies in Kano State despite the high frequency of use of insecticide-treated nets (ITNs) and indoor residual spraying in (Dawaki *et al.*, 2016; Oladele *et al.*, 2018). Different studies have been

Received: 12 August 2023

Revised: 20 August 2023

Final Accepted 2 September 2023

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8311436>

carried out in most parts of Nigeria especially mosquito endemic areas in North central Nigeria (Oguoma and Ikpeze, 2008), Zaria (Anyanwu and Iwuala, 1999) and Kano (Dawaki *et al.*, 2016) to ascertain and identify local mosquito species found in such areas. All of these efforts are targeted towards reducing or eliminating mosquito population at the most susceptible stage of their life cycle.

In human, malaria is caused by *Plasmodium falciparum*, *P. vivax*, *P. ovale*, and *P. malariae*. The infection by *P. falciparum* has been reported to pose the greatest threat (Geleta, 2016). *Anopheles gambiae* complex constitutes the main vector that transmits one of the most threatening *Plasmodium* species (*P. falciparum*) in sub-Saharan Africa (Kabula *et al.*, 2011). The *A. gambiae* complex consists of 7 species (*A. gambiae sensu stricto*, *A. arabiensis*, *A. quadriannulatus* species A and B, *A. melas*, *A. merus* and *A. bwambae*) which are morphologically indistinguishable. Recently, it has been reported that *A. gambiae sensu stricto* exists in 2 molecular forms, denoted M (now *A. coluzzii*) and S-form (now *A. gambiae* S.S.), which can be distinguished by differences in a 4-Mb region located in the X chromosome (Ranford-Cartwright *et al.*, 2016).

It was reported by WHO (1989) that more than three thousand species are distributed all over the world in a great variety of environment and most are found in the tropical and sub-tropical regions of the world with Nigeria inclusive. The breeding sites preference and physicochemical parameters of mosquitoes breeding sites of different mosquito species have been extensively studied and are relatively well understood (Felix *et al.*, 2016). *Anopheles gambiae* has been well studied in depth and certainly reported as the major vector of plasmodium continent-wide, it is frequently associated with other *Anopheles* species that override its importance in malaria transmission in certain area (WHO, 2011). In Nigeria *A. gambiae* has been described as being omnipresent because of its indiscriminate breeding habitats in such places like animal drinking places, domestic water containers and any other breeding places (Coetzee *et al.*, 2000). Also *A. arabiensis* has been described as a savannah vector in isolated populations, deforested areas and is predominant in the dry season (Wagbatsoma and Ogbeide, 1995). The nature of the study area (Makurdi) provides abundant breeding sites for mosquitoes. The prevalence of malaria is also high (Manyi *et al.*, 2014) and it caused by *Plasmodium* species using mosquito as vectors. The present study was undertaken as part of the ongoing malaria control programme in Benue State, Nigeria. The aim of this study was to determine the abundance and species composition of common mosquito species in Makurdi metropolis.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study area

Makurdi (the Capital of Benue State) is located in the North central area of Nigeria and it lies within the guinea Savannah region and has tropical climate with moderate rainfall that support abundant breeding sites for mosquitoes throughout the wet and dry seasons (Manyi *et al.*, 2014).

Received: 12 August 2023

Revised: 20 August 2023

Final Accepted 2 September 2023

Copyright © authors 2023

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8311436>

The town is intersected by River Benue- a major source of water that branch into networks of streams, standing pools, over filled and blocked drainages.

Figure 1: Map of Makurdi Local Government showing the Larval Sample Collection Localities and Sites. Source: Land and Survey, 2018.

Larval Sampling/Collection

Larval sampling for morphological assessment was carried out for a maximum cumulative period of one year (April 2021 to March 2022) from six locations in Makurdi using pole-mounted larval dipper with handle and clutches (WHO, 2005). The sample locations included Gboko Road, High level, Kanshio, North bank, Wadata and Wurukum respectively. Immature mosquitoes (larvae and pupae) were sampled from the edges of the pools and puddles at both below and at water surfaces by gently lowering the dipper at an angle of 45° with minimum disturbance to enable water and nearby larvae flow into it. Dipping was done at 1- 2 minutes intervals to enable the larvae which had swum downwards get back to the water surface.

Mosquito Breeding

All specimens collected from a particular breeding site were kept in one vial, labeled and transported to the Insectary Laboratory (B41, at Joseph Sarwuan Tarka University, Makurdi, designated for PMI/USAID Insecticide Resistance Testing Research). The containers were opened at intervals to allow the larvae and pupae to breathe. The larvae, which were obtained in the wild were emptied into larval rearing plastic pans filled with water from that same breeding habitat and maintained at 80 ± 10% RH and 25°-27°C. The larvae were fed twice daily with a mixture of

Received: 12 August 2023

Revised: 20 August 2023

Final Accepted 2 September 2023

Copyright © authors 2023

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8311436>

ground yeast and cabin biscuit (held in mesh covered glass tube), splashed over the surface of the rearing water.

Specimen identification

The specimens were identified morphologically using standard descriptor guide. Taxonomic keys/aids were used (Hopkins, 1952). Light microscopy was employed in further identification of parts. In occasions that the larvae could not be identified immediately, they were preserved using 4% formaldehyde solution as described by Olayemi *et al.* (2010) and subsequently identified by mosquito experts in the Department of Zoology, Joseph SarwuanTarka University, Makurdi Nigeria.

Data Analysis

Data analysis was done using the Chi square and analysis of variance tools of the SPSS 20.0 version. Decision was taken at 95% confidence limit ($P \leq 0.05$ level of significance).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 presents the species composition and abundance of *Anopheles* mosquitoes collected from six localities in the study area. A total of 1,902 samples and percentage frequency of 44.0% were recorded where Gboko road had the highest mosquito *Anopheles* mosquito samples of 397 (20.9%) dominated by *A. funestus* (21.8%) and *A. gambiae* (21.3%) in equal proportion. High Level was second highest in *Anopheles* mosquito samples with a total number of 382 samples (20.1%) and it was largely dominated by *A. gambiae* (23.2%). Kanshio location recorded the lowest number of samples with a total of 186 mosquitoes (9.8%). Statistically, abundance of *Anopheles* mosquito was the same in all location since Chi-square analysis did not show significant variation ($\chi^2 = 5.00$, $P = 0.416$ ($P > 0.05$)). In terms of *Anopheles* species distribution, the study area was dominated by *A. gambiae* with a total number of 1,040 samples collected with prevalence of 24.1% followed by *A. funestus* (14.8%) while the unidentified species accounted for 5.1%. Therefore, *Anopheles* mosquito abundance was dependent on the type of species as the observed differences among the species were significant ($\chi^2 = 12.31$, $P = 0.002$ ($P < 0.05$)). Percentage abundance of *A. gambiae* was highest at High Level location (23.2%) while *A. funestus* was mostly found at Wurukum location (22.2%).

Table 2 gives the monthly species composition and abundance of mosquito species which cut across two seasons (wet and dry) in the study area. From the study, additional mosquito species *Culex quinquefasciatus* was found and it recorded the highest abundance of 2418 (56.0%) among all the species found (Figure 2) out of a total number of 4,320 samples collected within 12 months. Mosquito abundance was at its peak in the month of June 2021 (558; 12.9%) and it was lowest in October (174; 4.0%). Mosquito abundance across the 12 months duration was the same as the

observed variation was not significant ($F = 0.00$, $P=1.000$; $P>0.05$). However, the variation in abundance of mosquito among the species was significant ($F = 66.81$, $P=0.000$; $P<0.05$). The population of *Anopheles* species was predominant in the wet seasons (April- September, 2011) than during the dry season (October, 2011- March, 2022). *Culex quinquefasciatus* had its peaks of abundance in April, 2021 [265 (52.7%)] and March, 2022 [302 (58.9%)]. *Anopheles gambiae* was abundant in August and September, 2021, with frequencies of 225(40.3%) and 141(24.8%) respectively. *Anopheles funestus* had a similar pattern of occurrence in May, 2021 {225 (40.3%)} and February, 2022 {120 (23.5%)} respectively. Generally, mosquito was most abundant from August to October with the peak in September (Figure 3)

Three species of mosquitoes were morphologically identified from the six settlements in Makurdi viz; *Culex quinquefasciatus*, *Anopheles gambiae* and *Anopheles funestus*. The dominant mosquito species in the study area was *C. quinquefasciatus* (56.0%), followed by *A. gambiae* (24.0%). This is in conformity with the report of Noutcha (2014) who found *C. quinquefasciatus* to be the dominant species in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. This is also in agreement with the report of Adeleke *et al.* (2010) who reported that the large occurrence of *C. quinquefasciatus* is not surprising because of its preference for polluted water as witnessed in many localities of the study area. Similarly, Oduola *et al.* (2012) and Ebenezer *et al.* (2012) reported preponderance of *A. gambiae* over *A. arabiensis* in their respective study areas in Nigeria.

Some of the major determinants of mosquito larval distribution have been reported to include the size and nature of the breeding site, physico-chemical parameters of the sites, raining pattern and the presence/absence of predators (Adebote *et al.*, 2008; Idowu *et al.*, 2014). In the present study, the three species of mosquitoes that emerged from collected larvae are known to be efficient vectors of some parasitic disease. *Anopheles gambiae* and *A. funestus* transmit malaria while *C. quinquefasciatus* is an important vector for the transmission of *Wuchereria bancrofti* (Idowu *et al.*, 2014). Over-grown bushes and rice fields are prominent in the study area, even around residential houses and offices (Manyi *et al.*, 2014). The temperature in the region is characteristically high, ranging from 25°C - 39°C, which is perceived to speed up the development and hatching of mosquitoes' eggs and this may have an impact on transmission of vector diseases in the area. This study is an indication that malaria transmission in the study area might be persistent. It therefore calls for appropriate holistic control measures by all stakeholders in the public health sector.

Morphological identification has provided fast and cheap baseline information on the prevailing species of mosquito in the study area. However, it is limited in resolution as some samples could not be sufficiently identified as they combined features of two different species. This could be resolved using molecular evidences as suggested by some authors (Felix *et al.*, 2016; Ranford-Cartwright *et al.*, 2016) because genotypic characteristics are not influenced by the environment unlike phenotypic characteristics. Gene sequencing may be employed in further studies to differentiate among the unidentified species into their various strains taxa in line with the studies carried out by Ranford-Cartwright *et al.* (2016) who resolved *A.gambiense* complex into seven different species.

Received: 12 August 2023

Revised: 20 August 2023

Final Accepted 2 September 2023

Copyright © authors 2023

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8311436>

Table 1: Species Composition and Abundance of *Anopheles* Mosquitoes Collected from six Localities in Makurdi.

Mosquito Species	Locality/Number of mosquitoes Dissected (%)						TOTAL (%)
	High-Level	Wurukum	North-Bank	Wadata	Gboko Rd.	Kanshio	
<i>Anopheles gambiae</i>	241(23.2)	152(14.6)	121(11.6)	204(19.6)	222(21.3)	100(9.6)	1,040 (24.1)
<i>Anopheles funestus</i>	114(17.8)	142(22.2)	117(18.3)	67(10.5)	140(21.8)	61(9.5)	641 (14.8)
<i>Anopheles</i> (unidentified)	27(12.2)	43 (19.5)	35 (15.8)	56(25.3)	35(15.8)	25(11.3)	221(5.1)
Total	382(20.1)	337(17.7)	273(14.4)	327(17.2)	397(20.9)	186(9.8)	1,902(44.0)

(a)Species: χ^2 (2df) = 12.31, P= 0.002 (P<0.05): Species composition is significantly different

(b)Locations: χ^2 (5df) = 5.00, P= 0.416 (P>0.05): Species composition is the same across all locations (location independent)

Table 2: Total Monthly Species Composition and Abundance of Mosquito Species Collected from Makurdi.

Month of Study	Total No. of Mosquitoes collected	Species of Mosquitoes(%)				TOTAL (%)
		<i>Culex quinquefasciatus</i>	<i>Anopheles gambiae</i>	<i>Anopheles funestus</i>	<i>Anopheles</i> species Unidentified	
April, 2021	503	265(52.7)	126(25.0)	102(20.3)	10(2.0)	503(11.6)
May, 2021	558	202(36.2)	225(40.3)	109(19.5)	22(3.9)	558(12.9)
June, 2021	569	289(50.8)	141(24.8)	120(21.1)	19(3.3)	569(13.2)

Received: 12 August 2023

Revised: 20 August 2023

Final Accepted 2 September 2023

Copyright © authors 2023

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8311436>

July, 2021	321	229(71.3)	53(16.5)	31(9.7)	8(2.5)	321(7.4)
August, 2021	202	162(80.2)	21(10.4)	10(4.9)	9(4.5)	202(4.7)
September, 2021	186	165(88.7)	10(5.4)	6(3.2)	5(2.7)	186(4.3)
October, 2021	174	130(74.7)	22(12.6)	8(4.6)	14(8.0)	174(4.0)
November, 2021	178	127(71.3)	29(16.3)	14(7.5)	8(2.5)	178(4.1)
December, 2021	297	176(59.3)	66(22.2)	31(10.4)	24(8.1)	297(6.9)
January, 2022	309	103(33.3)	111(35.9)	62(20.1)	33(10.7)	309(7.1)
February, 2022	510	268(52.5)	120(23.5)	75(14.7)	47(9.2)	510(11.8)
March, 2022	513	302(58.9)	116(22.6)	73(14.2)	22(4.3)	513(11.9)
TOTAL	4,320	2,418(56.0)	1,040(24.1)	641(14.8)	221(5.1)	4,320(100.0)

F (Time) = 0.00, P=1.000 (P>0.05)- No significance difference in time with respect to species composition
F (Species) = 66.81, P=0.000 (P<0.05)- Significance difference exists among the species

Figure 2 Proportion of the Mosquito Species found in the Study Area.

Figure 3: Composition and Abundance of *Anopheles* Mosquitoes .

CONCLUSION

Three species of mosquito identified in this study were *Culex quinquefasciatus* (the most abundant), *Anopheles gambiae* and *A. funestus*. Gboko road had the highest number of *Anopheles* mosquito samples while Kanshio location recorded the lowest. While *A. gambiae* was highest at High Level location *A. funestus* was mostly found at Wurukum location. The population of *Anopheles* species was more predominant in the wet seasons (April- September, 2011) than during the dry season (October, 2011- March, 2022). *Culex quinquefasciatus* had its peaks of abundance in April, 2021 [265 (52.7%)] and March, 2022 [302 (58.9%)]. This information may be useful in the control of mosquito and malaria infection in Makurdi, Benue State.

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Received: 12 August 2023

Revised: 20 August 2023

Final Accepted 2 September 2023

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8311436>

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